

EFFECT OF MANUFACTURING PARAMETERS ON THE QUALITY OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES MADE BY AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT (AFP)

S. V. Hoa¹, F. Shadmehri², J. F. Simpson³, M. I. El-Geuchy⁴

Mechanical & Industrial Engineering, Concordia University, Montreal, Canada
Center for Research in Polymers and Composites (CREPEC)

hoasuon@encs.concordia.ca, f.shadmehri@gmail.com, jeff_fs@hotmail.com
mr_geuchy@yahoo.com

Keywords: Automated fiber placement (AFP), Thermoplastic composites, Repass in-situ treatment, In-situ Consolidation, Surface quality, Roughness

ABSTRACT

One of the important requirements for composite structures used in aerodynamic applications is surface finish quality. In manufacturing of thermoplastic composite structures for aerodynamic applications, it is not only desirable to reach good consolidation by using fiber placement process alone, but also to achieve acceptable surface smoothness required for aero-surface structures. In this study, a novel in-situ treatment called “repass” is implemented to achieve surface finish quality required for aerodynamic applications. Moreover, the effect of repass treatment parameters on the surface roughness of the AFP-made samples was studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Technical advances in the automated manufacturing of thermoplastic composites have increasingly attracted the interests of the aerospace industry due to flexibility of the process allowing fabrication of complex composite parts. Specifically, Automated fiber placement (AFP) has provided a new look in the manufacturing of large-scale thermoplastic composite aero-structures in comparison with the traditional manufacturing processes.

In manufacturing of thermoplastic composite part, it is highly desirable to reach good quality by using fiber placement process alone and to avoid additional autoclave process to reduce manufacturing cost. However, due to various parameters involved in AFP process, achieving desirable quality of the AFP-made part is challenging [1-4]. Previous studies point out that the quality of fiber placed thermoplastic composites strongly depends on the manufacturing parameters such as temperature, compaction force (consolidation pressure) and layup speed [5-8].

One of the important requirements for structures categorized as aero-surface is the surface roughness and surface waviness. The surface finish has direct impact on the amount of drag and lift generated as airstream flows over the structure. Traditional in-situ manufacturing of thermoplastic composites using AFP, generally leads to a very rough surface, if layup is performed on a male tool (e.g., mandrel). Thus, it is highly desirable to achieve a good surface finish using an in-situ treatment technique in applications where aerodynamic requires smooth surface finish. In this study, a novel in-situ treatment called “repass” has been implemented to primarily improve the surface finish quality of the thermoplastic composites for aerodynamic application. Initially, a thermoplastic tube was manufactured with and without “repass” treatment to prove the concept in improving surface finish of the sample. Consequently, thirteen other samples with different “repass” treatment parameters (i.e., number of repasses, torch temperature and compaction force) were manufactured to study the effect of these parameters on the surface quality of the samples.

2 PROOF OF CONCEPT; IN-SITU TREATMENT TECHNIQUE

In order to primarily improve the surface finish quality of thermoplastic parts made by AFP, a novel in-situ treatment called “repass” has been implemented. The “repass” treatment can be simply explained as reapplying temperature and consolidation pressure to already laid laminate by repassing the AFP head on the laminate without supplying any additional material.

To prove the concept, a 4-inch diameter tube was made out of ¼-inch Carbon fiber/PEEK tape (supplied by TenCate Advanced Composites Company). The tube has 6 layers with stacking sequence of $[(90)_5/45]_T$ (i.e. the last layer is 45 degree). The first section of the tube was kept without any extra treatment while the middle section of the tube was treated by one time applying the repass treatment and end section of the tube was treated with two times repass treatment. The untreated 1st section of the tube was used as a baseline in roughness measurements to show surface finish improvement. The manufacturing and repass parameters used in this trial are listed in Table 1.

	Torch Temp. (°C)	Compaction force (lb)	Layup speed (in/sec)	Nitrogen flow rate (SLPM)
Manufacturing	910	80	3	75
Repass treatment	910	80	3	75

Table 1: Manufacturing and repass parameters of the 1st sample as a proof of concept

To demonstrate the effect of the repass treatment on the surface finish quality of the samples, the roughness parameters called “Maximum Height Deviation”, R_z , is measured. R_z is the mean values of Z_i which is defined as the summation of profile peak height, P_i , and profile valley depth, V_i within each sampling length (i.e., $Z_i = P_i + V_i$) (see Figure 1). The surface roughness of the tube was measured using a Mitutoyo SJ-400 surface roughness tester; the setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Profile definition, Z_i

Figure 2: Roughness measurement setup

The aforementioned roughness parameter (R_z) is reported in Table 2 for measurement along the longitudinal direction of the tube, for samples without repass treatment and with 1 and 2 times repass treatment. Typical roughness graphs are also shown in Figure 3.

Sample condition	R_z (μm)
Without repass	110.68
1 time repass treatment	37.15
2 times repass treatment	34.48

Table 2: Roughness measurement (sampling length= 2.5mm No. of samples=5)

Figure 3: Typical effect of the “repass” on roughness along the longitudinal direction

As it can be seen from Table 2, the repass treatment improves significantly surface roughness along the longitudinal direction by about 3.2 times. This result is very promising and proves the concept of applying repass in-situ treatment to improve surface finish quality of thermoplastic composites made by AFP. To investigate more in detail the effect of some of process parameters involved in repass treatment,

three parameters, namely, hot gas torch temperature, roller compaction force and number of repress treatments, were selected for study as explained in the following sections.

3 MANUFACTURING OF SAMPLES

In order to investigate the effect of aforementioned repress parameters, a 4.3 feet long tube with diameter of 4-inch was manufactured using a robotic type AFP at Concordia Center for Composites (CONCOM) lab (Figure 4) using ¼-inch Carbon fiber/PEEK tape (supplied by TenCate Advanced Composites Company). The tube had 6 layers with stacking sequence of $[90]_6$ (i.e. the last layer is 90 degree) and was made with manufacturing parameters mentioned in Table 1. The tube had 13 different sections treated with different repress parameters (i.e., hot gas torch temperature, roller compaction force and number of repress treatments). The torch temperature was varied between 910 °C and 950 °C, the roller compaction force was changed at three levels, namely, 80 lb, 100 lb and 120 lb and the number of repress treatments was varied between 2 and 3. The experiment design is shown in Table 3.

Figure 4: Manufacturing setup at Concordia Center for Composites (CONCOM)

4 EFFECT OF REPASS TREATMENT PARAMETERS ON SURFACE QUALITY

The surface roughness of the 13 samples manufactured using different repress treatment parameters was measured using a Mitutoyo SJ-400 surface roughness tester and the results are shown in Table 3. As can be seen, sample#1 was not treated by repress and had the roughest surface finish (R_z value of 168.7 μm) while sample#6 with 3 times repress treatments with torch temperature of 910 °C and compaction force of 100 lb has the smoothest surface finish (R_z value of 39.5 μm).

Sample #	Number of repasses	Torch Temp. (°C)	Compaction force (lb)	Roughness R_z (μm)
1	0	-	-	168.7
2	2	910	80	60.7
3	2	910	100	46.7
4	2	910	120	73.5
5	3	910	80	53.9
6	3	910	100	39.5
7	3	910	120	65.2
8	2	950	80	65.3
9	2	950	100	55.5
10	2	950	120	68.5
11	3	950	80	59.4
12	3	950	100	64.2
13	3	950	120	66.7

Table 3: Samples with different repass treatment parameters

Figure 5 shows the effect of different repass treatment parameters on the surface roughness of the samples. As a general trend at torch temperature equal to 910 °C, surface roughness improves as the compaction force increases from 80 lb to 100 lb and then deteriorates as the force keep increasing to 120 lb. This trend could be attributed to the fact that not enough compaction force or excessive compaction force both have detrimental effect on surface roughness. Another trend that can be seen from Figure 5 is that, at torch temperature equal to 910 °C, increasing the number of repass treatment from 2 to 3 improves surface roughness. The preliminary experiment performed to prove the concept (section 2) also shows that increasing the number of repasses from 1 to 2 improves surface roughness (Table 2). Another observation from Figure 5 is that increasing torch temperature from 910 °C to 950 °C causes rougher surface. This might be because excessive heat could burn a very thin layer of resin on the top layer and pull out some fibers, which led to deterioration of the surface finish of the sample. Another possibility is that at high temperature (i.e., 950 °C) resin becomes soft and cause lateral movement of the fibers, which in turn causes rougher surface.

Figure 5: Effect of re-pass treatment parameters on surface roughness

5 EFFECT OF RE-PASS TREATMENT ON VOID CONTENT

Previous studies suggested that re-pass treatment reduces interplay voids due to better wetting of fibers and better intimate contact between layers, however, it does not have an effect on fiber volume fraction since the resin entrapped inside laminate cannot be squeezed out by re-pass treatment [9]-[11]. If the primary goal is to reduce void content, it is suggested that re-pass treatment to be applied after material deposition at each layer. However, in this study, the main goal was to achieve surface finish quality appropriate for aerodynamic applications; thus, re-pass treatment only applied at the last ply. Micrographs obtained from different samples suggest that while void content is reduced close to the last ply, overall void content did not change considerably (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Micrograph (a) sample#1 without re-pass treatment (b) sample#6 with re-pass treatment

6 CONCLUSION

To achieve surface finish quality appropriate for aerodynamic applications, a novel in-situ treatment called “re-pass” has been implemented in in-situ manufacturing of thermoplastic composites made by Automated Fiber Placement (AFP). A proof-of-concept trial showed a significant improvement in surface roughness of Carbon fiber/PEEK tubes upon implementing the re-pass treatment. A study of a few re-pass treatment parameters, namely, torch temperature, roller compaction force and number of re-pass treatments, was performed to determine the effect of these parameters on the surface roughness of the samples.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The financial support from the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada is appreciated.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Shadmehri, X. Cai, M. Hojjati, J. Chen, S. V. Hoa, Determination of optimal process parameters for manufacturing thermoplastic composite rings by automated fiber placement, *American Society for Composites (ASC), 26th Technical Conference (the second joint US-Canada conference on composites)*, Montreal, Canada, September 2011.
- [2] X. Cai, F. Shadmehri, M. Hojjati, J. Chen, S. Hoa, Determination of Optimum Process Conditions for Processing AS4/APC-2 Thermoplastic Composites by Automated Fiber Placement, *The Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering (SAMPE) conference*, Baltimore, MD, May 2012.
- [3] J. Fortin-Simpson, M. I. El-Geuchy, F. Shadmehri and S. V. Hoa, Effect of processing parameters on the bending behavior of thermoplastic composite tubes made by automated fiber placement process, *American Society for Composites (ASC), 28th Technical Conference*, State College, PA, 2013.
- [4] S. V. Hoa, *Principles of the Manufacturing of Composite Materials*. DEStech Publications, Inc., 2009.
- [5] A. Yousefpour, M. N. Ghasemi Nejjhad, Experimental and Computational Study of APC-2/AS4 Thermoplastic Composite C-Rings, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 14(2), 2001, pp. 129-145.
- [6] M. N. Ghasemi Nejjhad, R. D. Cope and S. I. Güçeri, Thermal Analysis of In-Situ Thermoplastic-Matrix Composite Tape Laying, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 4(1), 1990, pp. 29-45.
- [7] M. N. Ghasemi Nejjhad, Issues Related to Processibility during the Manufacture of Thermoplastic Composite Using On-Line Consolidation Technique, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 6, 1993, pp. 130-145.
- [8] M. Hojjati, G. Chouinard, A. Yousefpour, Crystallization Behavior of PEKK Thermoplastic Polymer, *The Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering (SAMPE) conference*, Long Beach, California. April 30, 2006 – May 4, 2006.
- [9] Mohamed Ibrahim El-Geuchy, *Bending Behavior of Thick-Walled Composite Tubes*, Ph.D. Thesis, Concordia University, April 2013.
- [10] Minh Duc Hoang, *Procedure for making flat thermoplastic composite plates by Automated Fiber Placement and their mechanical properties*, M.Sc. Thesis, Concordia University, April 2015.
- [11] S. V. Hoa, Minh Duc Hoang and Jeff Simpson, Manufacturing Procedure to Make Flat Thermoplastic Composite Laminates by Automated Fibre Placement and Their Mechanical Properties, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, First Published 16 Sep 2016.